

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY INDICATORS IN CHILDREN WITH DIFFERENT TYPES OF CHOLECYSTITIS (INFECTIOUS AND NON-INFECTIOUS)

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Abstract. *Chronic inflammatory diseases of the biliary tract in children are among the most pressing issues in modern pediatric gastroenterology. Inflammatory processes and impaired bile passage can contribute to both functional and organic disorders of the liver and intestines, as well as cause dysbiotic alterations of the microbiocenosis in the distal sections of the small and large intestines. This article presents a comparative analysis of anamnestic data and clinical-laboratory parameters in children with various forms of cholecystitis of infectious and non-infectious etiology. The obtained results help clarify the clinical course, laboratory profile, and underlying factors contributing to the development of inflammatory biliary tract diseases in childhood.*

Keywords: *biliary tract, cholecystitis, clinical and laboratory parameters.*

Introduction. Chronic inflammatory diseases of the biliary tract are among the most common pathologies of the digestive system in children. According to various authors, patients with chronic cholecystitis account for 17–20% of cases [1,2,4]. Inflammatory processes and disorders of bile passage may contribute to the development of functional and organic pathologies of the liver and intestines, as well as disturbances of the microbiocenosis in the distal parts of the small and large intestine [7,8,9].

At first glance, it is not always possible to determine the primary cause of a disease affecting a particular organ of the gastrointestinal tract, since very complex functional interrelationships exist among these organs [3,6,8]. However, along with the diagnosis of chronic cholecystitis, the timely detection of associated functional and morphological disorders of adjacent organs (the liver, intestines, and others) can help prevent the development of severe complications.

In view of the above, the aim of this study was to investigate the characteristics of chronic cholecystitis and its effect on the state of the intestinal biocenosis, as well as on the development of pathological changes in other organs. To achieve this aim, 72 children aged 7–14 years diagnosed with chronic cholecystitis in the exacerbation stage were examined. Among the patients, there were 32 boys (44.4%) and 49 girls (55.6%). The mean age of the patients was 11.9 ± 1.9 years. The collection of research material and clinical examinations were conducted in the somatic department of the 4th City Children's Clinical Hospital in Tashkent. Patient groups were formed using a random sampling method as they presented to the institution for examination.

The diagnosis in the examined patients was verified based on medical history and clinical data, laboratory indicators, instrumental examinations, and bile analysis obtained during duodenal intubation. The first stage of the study involved the analysis of the frequency of certain clinical symptoms and laboratory findings in the examined patients during the initial examination. All

patients were admitted in a state of exacerbation of chronic cholecystitis or were actively identified. Clinical examination of the children at presentation showed that, in the overwhelming majority of cases, patients exhibited one or more symptoms of the disease (Table 1).

Presence of disease symptoms and general condition of patients at the time of presentation (n = 72).

Indicators	Abs	% (M±m)
Body constitution:		
Asthenic	28	38,8±5,7
Normosthenic	32	44,4±5,8
Hypersthenic	11	15,2±4,2
Palatine Tonsils:		
Hypertrophied	27	37,5±5,7
Atrophied	15	20,8±4,7
Nervous system disorders	51	70,8±5,2
Cardiovascular System Disorders:		
Muffled heart sounds	39	54,1±5,8
Heart rate and rhythm disturbances	13	18,0±4,5
Gastrointestinal Manifestations:	72	100
Flatulence	38	52,7±5,8
Abdominal rumbling	54	75,0±5,1
Pain Points and Clinical Signs:	72	100,0
Kerr's sign (+)	69	95,8±2,3
Mussi's sign (+)	54	75,0±5,1
Grekov–Ortner sign (+)	56	77,7±4,9
Murphy's sign (+)	65	90,2±3,5
Lepene's sign (+)	22	30,5±5,4
Enlargement of Liver Borders	18	25,0±5,1
Intestinal Pain:		95,8±2,3
Tenderness of the transverse colon	69	27,7±5,2
Pain and spasm of the sigmoid colon	20	76,3±5,0

Based on the presented data, it is evident that all patients (100%) exhibited various clinical manifestations of gastrointestinal tract pathology, particularly involving the biliary tract and gallbladder. Physical examination revealed positive Kerr, Mussey, Grekov–Ortner, Murphy, and Lepene signs in children (30.5–95.8%), tenderness and spasm of the sigmoid colon (76.3%), intestinal meteorism (52.7%), and enlargement of the liver borders (25.0%).

In addition to gastrointestinal disturbances, disorders affecting other organs and systems were also observed. From the cardiovascular system, muffled heart sounds were noted in 54.1% of cases, as well as rhythm and heart rate disturbances in 18.0% of patients. Regarding the nervous system, as previously indicated, rapid fatigability (66.6%), sleep disturbances (41.6%), irritability (55.5%), headache and dizziness (22.2%), and other manifestations characteristic of chronic intoxication syndrome were recorded.

For the diagnosis of cholecystitis, instrumental diagnostic methods are required, including ultrasonographic examination of the liver, gallbladder, pancreas, and spleen (Table 2).

Ultrasound examination of the patients revealed significant changes in the gallbladder. Signs of inflammation were observed in all patients (100%). In 36.1% of children, inflammatory manifestations were accompanied by alterations in bile composition, and in 19.4% of cases, deformities of the gallbladder body and neck were noted, which also contributed to the persistence of the inflammatory process. It should be noted that in children with chronic cholecystitis, various organs of the gastrointestinal tract are frequently involved. In our patients, 25.1% showed liver changes, while no echographic signs of pancreatic pathology were detected. The spleen rarely exhibited significant alterations—3 cases (4.1%).

Baseline ultrasound parameters of the examined patients (n = 72).

Ultrasound Findings	Abs..	% (M±m)
Liver:		
Increased echogenicity (parenchymal densification)	18	25,0±5,1
Gallbladder:		
Signs of chronic cholecystitis	72	100,0
Kinking at the neck region	6	8,3±3,2
Kinking at the body of the gallbladder	8	11,1±3,7
Sediment (sludge) in the gallbladder contents	26	36,1±5,6
Pancreas:	72	100,0
No pathological changes detected		
Spleen:	3	4,1±2,3
Splenomegaly		

Based on these findings, it was considered appropriate to divide the patients into two groups: those with infectious cholecystitis (Group 1) and those with non-infectious cholecystitis (Group 2). Clinical, laboratory, immunological, and immunocytochemical parameters were compared between the two groups to identify the relationship of these indicators with the etiology of cholecystitis. Additionally, the effects of infectious and non-infectious cholecystitis on other organs and systems, primarily the gastrointestinal and nervous systems, were assessed.

To ensure representativeness, the groups were compared in terms of sex, age, and various historical data. Analysis showed that the groups were comparable by sex and age.

However, children aged 10 years predominantly had non-infectious cholecystitis, whereas in the 12-year-old group, the disease was more often of infectious etiology ($P < 0.01$). A comparison of anamnesis data revealed that patients in both groups had histories of various infectious and non-infectious diseases that could contribute to the development of chronic cholecystitis (e.g., viral hepatitis, chickenpox, measles, mumps, acute intestinal infections, sinusitis, chronic tonsillitis, otitis, bronchitis, pneumonia, etc.). It was evident that in children with infectious cholecystitis, previous infectious diseases were the most significant contributing factor. Analysis showed that the mean number of previously experienced infectious (viral and bacterial) diseases per patient was 1.83 in Group 1 and 1.4 in Group 2. This suggests that the frequency of acute and chronic infections may influence the etiology of cholecystitis by promoting the infectious component of inflammation in the gallbladder and biliary tract, as well as by impairing local and systemic immunity and activating opportunistic pathogens in the gastrointestinal tract.

It was established that, regardless of etiology, all children exhibited a recurrent course of the disease. In the majority of cases, relapses in both groups were associated with gross nutritional violations (42 patients—100% in Group 1 and 28 patients—93.3% in Group 2). In some cases,

exacerbations in both groups were associated with seasonal factors: $21.4 \pm 6.3\%$ in autumn and $13.3 \pm 6.1\%$ in spring ($P > 0.05$).

It should also be noted that all patients (100%), regardless of cholecystitis etiology, had various comorbid conditions, including anemia, chronic ENT disorders, chronic upper respiratory tract diseases, diffuse thyroid enlargement, diabetes mellitus, orthopedic pathology, and visual organ diseases.

Analysis of blood biochemical parameters showed an increase in γ -glutamyltransferase (γ -GT) in both groups compared with healthy individuals. This indicator was higher in Group 1 than in Group 2, although the difference was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). No deviations from normal values were found for other biochemical tests (total protein, bilirubin, liver-specific enzymes, cholesterol, alkaline phosphatase, alpha-amylase, certain trace elements, etc.), and no significant differences between groups were detected ($P > 0.05$).

Microscopic analysis of bile obtained by duodenal intubation revealed that in Group 1 children, inflammation was more frequently accompanied by leukocytosis, desquamation of cylindrical epithelium, and changes in bile color and transparency ($P < 0.05 - < 0.001$).

Conclusion. Children with chronic cholecystitis exhibited pronounced clinical manifestations of gastrointestinal tract pathology, as well as disturbances in the nervous and cardiovascular systems. Instrumental examination detected signs of gallbladder inflammation in all patients, often accompanied by deformities and sediment in its contents. Comparative analysis showed that the infectious form was more often associated with marked inflammatory changes in bile and increased γ -GT, while in non-infectious forms, these differences were less pronounced. Significant deviations in key blood biochemical parameters were not observed. Thus, chronic cholecystitis in children has a recurrent course, is associated with nutritional violations and comorbid conditions, and requires a comprehensive clinical, laboratory, and instrumental diagnostic approach.

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